

SEEING WILDE SONGS

Charles T. Griffes' Synesthetic Musical Settings of Oscar Wilde's Poetry

Curated by: Dr. Zan Cammack, Lecturer, UVU Department of English and Literature

Venue: Museum of Art at Lakemount, Utah Valley University

Exhibition Dates: January 27, 2026 – May 23, 2026

Curatorial Statement

This exhibition was curated as a contribution to scholarship on cross-arts Impressionism, sensory aesthetics, and word and music studies of Oscar Wilde's poetry in Charles T. Griffes' American art songs.

Poetry, music, and painting often blur together. In the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, artists across Europe and North America began embracing this overlap, experimenting with ways to capture fleeting moments of sensation. Painters explored light and atmosphere, poets wrote in bursts of color and musical phrasing, and composers sought ways to give sound a visual or physical presence. This shared approach came to be known as Impressionism—a way of experiencing the world through shifting, overlapping senses.

Seeing Wilde Songs traces these crossings through the poetry of Oscar Wilde and the music of composer Charles T. Griffes. Griffes was drawn to Wilde's poems for their musical titles, rhythmic language, and vivid color imagery. In setting these works to music, Griffes reshaped Wilde's verse as sound, drawing out the sensory resonances already embedded in the poems.

For Griffes, this attraction to Wilde's sensory language was more than metaphor. He experienced synesthesia: a form of perception in which the senses cross. Certain musical notes appeared to him as specific colors. Wilde's luminous imagery—especially his repeated use of yellow and gold—thus became not only poetic description but a sensory catalyst, guiding Griffes' compositional choices and tonal color.

The exhibition incorporated twenty-five Impressionist and proto-Impressionist works in reproduction, selected to illuminate each poem's visual and sensory world. Works were presented as reproductions, a deliberate choice that prioritized the sensory and thematic relationships between image, poem, and music over object-based display. Audio recordings of each Griffes setting were commissioned for the exhibition and performed by UVU students, coordinated with the support of UVU music faculty. Throughout the gallery, each display brings together a poem, its musical setting, and a curated selection of visual art. As you move through the space, listen, look, and read for moments when sound seems to take on color, images suggest music, and poetry hovers between the senses.

The exhibition draws on archival sources, musicological scholarship, and literary analysis to reconstruct the sensory and intellectual world shared by Wilde and Griffes. It argues that synesthesia functions not merely as biographical footnote but as a structuring interpretive principle connecting these two artists across the boundaries of medium, sensory experience, and time.

Works Presented

Poetry by Oscar Wilde

Symphony in Yellow · La Fuite de la Lune · Le Jardin · Impression du Matin · La Mer · Le Réveillon · Les Ballons

Musical Settings by Charles T. Griffes

Four Impressions (1912–16) · *Tone Images*, Op. 3 (1915) · *Les Ballons* (c. 1912; rev. 1915)

Audio Recordings

The following recordings were commissioned for this exhibition by Utah Valley University:

Song	Voice	Piano	Source
Symphony in Yellow	Savannah Webb, soprano	Anna Peterson	UVU Commission
La Fuite de la Lune	Jan Opalach, baritone	Jeffrey Goldberg	Musical Heritage Society*
Le Jardin	Bethany Rasmussen, soprano	Jessica Allen	UVU Commission
Impression du Matin	Savannah Webb, soprano	Anna Peterson	UVU Commission
La Mer	Bethany Rasmussen, soprano	Jessica Allen	UVU Commission
Le Réveillon	Hélène Loosli, soprano	Anna Peterson	UVU Commission
Les Ballons	Hélène Loosli, soprano	Anna Peterson	UVU Commission

*La Fuite de la Lune performed by Jan Opalach (baritone) and Jeffrey Goldberg (piano). Recording courtesy of The Musical Heritage Society. All rights retained by the original rights holder.

Visual Art (Reproductions)

Artist	Work	Date
Knud Baade	Clouds in Moonlight	1843
Eugène Boudin	Beach at Trouville	1863
Gustave Courbet	The Wave (La Vague)	1870
Johan Christian Dahl	Skyer i måneskinn (Clouds in Moonlight)	1847
Henry Dawson	St Paul's from the River Thames	1877
Arthur Gilbert	The Rising Moon	1853
Eva Gonzalès	Morning Awakening	1887
Edward Atkinson Hornel	Balloons at Brighthouse Bay	1929
Johan Barthold Jongkind	Harbor by Moonlight	1871
Henri Le Sidaner	St. Paul's from the River – Morning Sun in Winter	1907

Artist	Work	Date
Claude Monet	Impression, Sunrise (Impression, soleil levant)	1872
Claude Monet	Poplars on the Banks of the River Epte seen from the Marsh	1892
Berthe Morisot	Le jardin à Bougival (The Garden at Bougival)	1884
Berthe Morisot	Dans les Blés (In the Wheatfield)	1875
Maurice Prendergast	The Balloon	1898
Pierre-Auguste Renoir	The Garden in the Rue Cortot	1876
Pierre-Auguste Renoir	Woman with a Parasol in a Garden	1875
David Roberts	St Paul's From The Thames	1863
Dante Gabriel Rossetti	Found	1854
Alfred Sisley	The Seine near Bougival, Winter Morning	1874
Adalbert Stifter	Mondlandschaft mit bewölktem Himmel	1850
J.M.W. Turner	Snow Storm: Steam-Boat off a Harbour's Mouth	1842
J.M.W. Turner	The Thames above Waterloo Bridge	1830
James McNeill Whistler	Nocturne: Blue and Gold – Old Battersea Bridge	1875
James McNeill Whistler	Nocturne in Gray and Gold, Westminster Bridge	1874

Acknowledgments

The exhibition was realized in collaboration with Emily Johnsen, Museum Director, and Taylor Wright, Exhibition Designer (Utah Valley University Museum of Art at Lakemount), whose work gave curatorial vision its physical form.

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